

**EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR
CHARACTERISTICS****Jumayev Elbek Ergashevich**

Researcher

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the content of the concept of educational technologies, their role and importance in the educational process, as well as the specific characteristics of modern pedagogical technologies. The article analyzes ways to increase the effectiveness of the educational process through the use of innovative and interactive educational technologies..

The reforms taking place in the education system today require, first of all, the implementation of new forms and methods of teaching. Educational technologies are methods for organizing the educational process on a systematic, planned and scientific basis, effectively managing it and directing it to the result.

The purpose of introducing pedagogical technologies is to comprehensively develop the student's personality, to teach them independent thinking, analysis, and creative approach. Therefore, today it is becoming necessary to organize the educational process on a technological basis.

The term "educational technology" means a set of methods, tools, forms and techniques necessary for the effective organization of the educational process. This system involves managing the educational process not only theoretically, but also practically.

Pedagogical technologies consist of the following components:

Goal setting (result orientation);

Selection and systematization of educational content;

Application of interactive methods;

Use of information and communication technologies;

Assessment and analysis of learning outcomes.

Today, the following main technologies are widely used in education:

1. Traditional pedagogical technologies - teaching methods organized on the basis of a teacher-centered approach.

2. Innovative technologies - methods that develop new thinking, creativity and independence (project method, cluster, "brainstorming", debate, etc.).

3. Information and communication technologies (ICT) - organization of education in an interactive form through the use of digital tools, computer programs, Internet platforms.

4. Distance learning technologies - teaching based on online classes, virtual learning environments and electronic resources.

5. Modular educational technology - a system that divides the educational process into small sections (modules) and allows you to independently master each stage.

Educational technologies have the following specific features:

Effectiveness - a specific learning outcome is achieved at the end of each lesson.

Systematicity - the learning process is organized in a step-by-step, logical sequence.

Interactivity - there is constant communication between the teacher and the student.

Adaptability - the possibility of an approach that is appropriate to the individual abilities of the student is created.

Control and analysis - learning outcomes are regularly assessed and analyzed.

Integration with technical means - the use of digital educational resources, multimedia and artificial intelligence technologies.

The implementation of pedagogical technologies in practice leads to the following results:

The activity and interest of students increases;

Independent learning and creative thinking skills are formed;

The atmosphere of cooperation between the teacher and the student is strengthened;

The quality and effectiveness of education increases;

Digital competencies are developed in the learning process.

In conclusion, educational technologies are one of the most important factors in the effective organization and result-orientedness of the educational process. They activate the teaching process, provide a person-centered approach, and develop the creative potential of students. Each teacher can raise the quality of education to a new level by implementing modern technologies in his work.

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